

Notes

Complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with Bidentate Schiff's Base

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IN our programme of preparing complexes of rare and higher coordination number with first transition series metal ions, we have been synthesising number of polydentate chelating ligands, since such ligands dominate the area of higher coordination polyhedra from kinetic and thermodynamic stability point of view. Earlier, we have studied¹⁻⁵ the complexation behaviour of a number of *bi*-, *tri*- and *tetra*-dentate schiff's bases. This communication reports complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), and Zn(II) ions with a bidentate schiff's base derived from salicylaldehyde and 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Salicylaldehyde-2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone was prepared by the conventional method.

An ethanolic solution of the Schiff's base was reacted with ethanolic solution of metal chlorides in (2 : 1) ratio followed by dropwise addition of ammonia, when the metal chelate separated. These were filtered, washed with ethanol and ether and dried in vacuo.

Metal in the complexes was estimated by EDTA titration method and nitrogen by microanalytical method. Conductance was measured in M/1000 D.M.F. or chloroform solution of the complexes. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made over solid specimens by Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr phase using Perkin-Elmer model 337 and 621 spectrophotometers.

Electronic spectra were recorded in M/100 chloroform solution using a Hilger-Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer. All the relevant, analytical, magnetic susceptibility and spectral data are recorded in Table-1.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have the composition $[ML_2(H_2O)_2]$ where M = Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) and L is the anion of the schiff's bases¹ derived from salicylaldehyde and 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazine. All are crystalline compounds. Cobalt complex is brown, nickel and copper are green and zinc is brownish white. These have low conductance values, indicating non-electrolytic nature of complexes. Magnetic moment values are indicative of the presence of three, two and one unpaired electrons in case of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes respectively and suggest an octahedral configuration of these compounds.

Although there are three sites for coordination *viz* oxygen of the -OH group, nitrogen of $\nu(C=N)$ and nitrogen of -NH, bonding has actually taken place through the oxygen and azomethine nitrogen atoms. $\nu(C=N)$ usually occurs $\sim 1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which has decreased to lower frequency region (on coordination) due to the reduction of electron density⁴⁻⁵ in the azomethine link. $\nu(C-O)$ appears $\sim 1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region. A medium broad band appears around 3450 cm^{-1} region assignable to $\nu(O-H)$ of coordinated water molecule present. The sharp band due to $\nu(N-H)$ has probably been superimposed in this broad band envelope. Decrease in both $\nu(C-O)$ and $\nu(C=N)$ compared to the ligand suggests bonding at these sites. This has been further substantiated by the observation of two bands at 450 and $\sim 510\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable⁶ to $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ respectively in the far infrared spectra of complexes.

In the visible electronic spectra, two absorption bands appear at 18 8(35) and 8.5(20) k.k. attributable to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ transitions respectively. Position of absorption bands, molar absorptivity values and magnetic moment suggests a high-spin octahedral configuration for the cobalt(II) complex. Nickel(II) complex

TABLE-1 ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY AND I.R. SPECTRAL DATA

Compound	M.P °C	∇M (mhos cm^2)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	% metal		% N		Infrared spectra cm^{-1}			
				Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	$\nu(C=N)$	$\nu(C-O)$	$\nu(M-O)$	$\nu(M-N)$
$[\text{CoL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	200	16 (DMF)	4.9	8.12	8.27	17.81	17.95	1595	1200	450	510
$[\text{NiL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	170	17 (DMF)	2.9	7.97	8.22	17.77	17.95	1580	1210	460	500
$[\text{CuL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	210	5 (CHCl_3)	1.78	8.94	8.83	17.65	17.82	1585	1210	460	510
$[\text{ZnL}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	220 ^a	6 (CHCl_3)	-	9.21	9.09	17.58	17.77	1580	1200	450	510

^aDecomposition

exhibits three absorption bands at 8.8(6), 14.7(10) and 25.0(15) k.k. assignable⁷ to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}$ (P)⁸ transitions respectively characteristic of high-spin octahedral or distorted octahedral configuration. Copper(II) complex shows one broad absorption band at 15.5 (45) k.k. indicating probably a tetragonally distorted octahedral configuration. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data zinc(II) complexes presumably have an octahedral environment around the metal ion.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some Rare Earths With EDTA as Primary Ligand and 2,3-Dihydroxynaphthalene-6-Sulphonic Acid as Secondary Ligand : A Potentiometric Study

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In recent years, the study of the mixed ligand complexes of the rare earths has become of great interest, as its existence gives an evidence for the rare earths to have a coordination number greater than six and also offers an alternative reaction to the hydrolysis andolation of rare earths in binary complexes.

In the present paper, evidence for the mixed ligand complex formation are summarised which thereby explains the expansion in coordination number of rare earths due to replacement of water molecules by the second ligand. The stability constants of the binary and ternary complexes have been determined by using an extension of the Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique¹ to the mixed ligand complexes.

Experimental

The chemicals used during these investigations were of *analar* grade. The stock solution of 2,3-dihydroxynaphthalene-6-sulphonic acid (Light and Co. Ltd.), 0.01 M was prepared in double distilled water. Other solutions were prepared as described in previous papers.²⁻⁴ Experimental set up, instruments used, systems prepared etc. were same as in earlier studies²⁻⁴

Results and Discussion

The 'Practical' proton-ligand stability constants were obtained by the methods of interpolation at various \bar{n}_A -values (Method A) and interpolation at half \bar{n}_A -values (Method B). The values of $\log K_1^H$ and $\log K_2^H$ were found to be 11.39 and 8.10 (Method A), and 11.42 and 8.11 (Method B), respectively.

The stability constants of the binary complexes were obtained as reported earlier.^{2,8} The value of \bar{n} in the metal-ligand formation curve exceeded 1.5 which reveals the formation of 1 : 1 as well as 1 : 2 complexes. The values of 1 : 1 complexes only have been used for comparison purposes and are reported in Table 1.

The stability constants for the ternary complexes were evaluated as in previous paper⁴ The value of \bar{n} does not exceed 0.9 or 1.0 which shows the formation of only 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand complex. The values obtained are tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE-1 STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF DHNSA

$t = 30^\circ\text{C}$ and $\mu = 0.2 \text{ M NaClO}_4$

Metal	Binary		Ternary	
	A	B	A	B
Sc(III)	14.15	14.11	7.27	7.22
Y(III)	10.09	10.06	6.83	6.81
La(III)	8.35	8.31	4.68	4.64
Pr(III)	8.96	8.94	5.43	5.40
Nd(III)	9.10	9.03	5.60	5.57
Sm(III)	9.68	9.73	6.30	6.32

For all the rare earths, the stability constants of mixed ligand complexes are less than those of the corresponding (1 : 1) binary complexes which can be explained on the basis of electrostatic forces and space available for the second incoming ligand. In the present study, EDTA being a hexadentate ligand, occupies all the six coordination sites and thus satisfies the characteristic coordination number of six. Now to accommodate second ligand which is bidentate in nature, water molecules at seventh and eighth coordination sites are to be displaced. The formation of only 1 : 1 : 1 mixed-ligand chelate reveals the coordination number of eight for the

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